

A DeepONet Surrogate Model for Nuclide Prediction in Spent Fuel Using Transfer Learning

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DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.20803740

ABSTRACT

This paper introduces a surrogate model based on the Deep Operator Network (DeepONet) for high-accuracy, high-efficiency prediction of critical nuclide concentrations in spent nuclear fuel (SNF). The model innovatively decouples the burnup prediction problem by processing dynamic and static inputs separately: a Branch Net, composed of Gated Recurrent Units (GRU), accurately encodes the complex temporal dynamics of the reactor's power history. Concurrently, a Trunk Net, implemented as a Multi-Layer Perceptron (MLP), processes static initial conditions such as fuel enrichment. By fusing the features from these two branches, the model efficiently learns the operator mapping from input functions to final nuclide concentrations. To address the challenges of the "simulation-to-reality (Sim-to-Real) gap" in traditional physics simulations and the sparsity of experimental data, we designed a two-stage transfer learning framework. The model is first pre-trained on thousands of high-fidelity NUIT simulation cases to learn the general physical laws of burnup. Subsequently, it is fine-tuned on a small set of real experimental data to correct for systemic biases in the physical model. Experimental results demonstrate that the fine-tuned model exhibits outstanding predictive performance, comprehensively surpassing both pure physics simulations and models trained from scratch. Notably, for higher-order actinides such as Americium (Am) and Curium (Cm), the model successfully reduces the relative error from as high as 70%-90% in physics simulations down to the 5%-20% range. This research provides a novel, fast, and reliable paradigm for SNF analysis that fuses physics-based knowledge with experimental data.

Keywords: DeepONet, Surrogate Model, Burnup, Sim-to-Real, Transfer Learning

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1. Background and Motivation

Fuel burnup is a core physical process driven by neutron capture, fission, and radioactive decay, forming a complex transmutation chain [1]. The precise isotopic vector of the resulting hundreds of nuclides in spent nuclear fuel (SNF)—especially key actinides (U, Pu, Am, Cm) and long-lived fission products (LLFPs)—determines its macroscopic properties. These include decay heat, radiation source terms, and fissile content, which critically impact storage, disposal safety, and reprocessing feasibility.

Current state-of-the-art methods rely on high-fidelity, first-principles codes (e.g., Serpent [2], OpenMC [3]) that couple neutron transport with burnup equations. While accurate, this fidelity comes at an enormous computational cost, often requiring thousands of CPU-hours for a single full-life simulation. This "accuracy-efficiency" trade-off renders high-fidelity models impractical for "many-query" scenarios like fuel management optimization or online monitoring.

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1.2. The Need for Surrogate Models

Given the computational cost and inherent uncertainties (e.g., in nuclear data [4], modeling approximations, and operational history), developing fast and accurate surrogate models is an urgent need in modern nuclear engineering. A trained surrogate can perform predictions in fractions of a second, enabling applications previously deemed computationally infeasible, such as design optimization and the creation of real-time digital twins.

Recent advances in AI and machine learning (ML) have shown great promise. Early work used classical ML methods, but these struggled with high-dimensional, dynamic inputs like power history. Deep Neural Networks (DNNs) have demonstrated superior capability [5, 6, 7], but often oversimplify the problem by treating time-series inputs as static statistical features.

1.3. Methodological Innovation

This study proposes a calibrated, fast-response burnup surrogate model built on two innovative pillars:

1.3.1. Architectural Innovation: DeepONet for Operator Learning

Fundamentally, burnup prediction is an operator learning problem. This is because the final nuclide concentration is not determined merely by static initial conditions (like initial nuclide content); rather, it is a product of the entire dynamic process of the reactor's operational history.

We employ the Deep Operator Network (DeepONet) [8], a framework grounded in the universal approximation theorem for operators. Its unique Branch/Trunk architecture is perfectly suited to this task, allowing the model to learn the intrinsic physical structure of the problem rather than performing simple curve fitting.

1.3.2. Paradigm Innovation: Sim-to-Real Transfer Learning

To bridge the "Sim-to-Real gap" and overcome the extreme scarcity of experimental data, we design a two-stage transfer learning process [9]:

1. Physics-informed Pre-training: The DeepONet is first pre-trained on a large-scale, high-fidelity simulation dataset (from the NUIT code) covering a wide parameter space. This stage imbues the model with general-purpose knowledge of burnup physics.
2. Experiment-driven Fine-tuning: The pre-trained model is then fine-tuned on a small, high-value dataset of real Post-Irradiation Examination (PIE) experimental measurements. This stage calibrates the model, teaching it to correct for the systemic biases present in the simulation.

Our primary contribution is the novel synthesis of DeepONet-based operator learning with a Sim-to-Real transfer learning paradigm to solve a complex, dynamic problem in nuclear engineering. The resulting model is shown to be not just a fast approximation, but a data-enhanced tool that is more accurate than the simulation model it was built upon.

2. METHODOLOGY: MODEL AND TRAINING

2.1. The DeepONet Framework

While classical DNNs learn mappings $f : \mathbb{R}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^m$, DeepONet learns an operator $\mathcal{G} : \mathcal{U} \rightarrow \mathcal{V}$. Here, \mathcal{U} is a space of input functions, and \mathcal{V} is the corresponding space of output functions. The operator \mathcal{G} maps an entire input function $u \in \mathcal{U}$ to a specific output function $v \in \mathcal{V}$, such that $v = \mathcal{G}(u)$.

The goal is to predict the value of this output function v at a specific query point, we will call this query point (the input to the Trunk Net) ξ . The model then learns to predict $v(\xi) = \mathcal{G}(u)(\xi)$.

DeepONet achieves this by decomposing the operator into two sub-networks, as shown in Figure 1:

- Branch Net (N_{branch}): Encodes the input function $u(t)$ into a fixed-length feature vector $b \in \mathbb{R}^p$.
- Trunk Net (N_{trunk}): Encodes the query location ξ into another feature vector $t \in \mathbb{R}^p$.

The outputs are then combined (e.g., via dot product) and passed through a final layer to produce the prediction, \hat{y} , which approximates the true value $\mathcal{G}(u)(\xi)$:

$$\mathcal{G}_\theta(u, \xi) \approx \hat{y} = \sum_{k=1}^p b_k(u) t_k(\xi) \quad (1)$$

Figure 1. Conceptual architecture of the DeepONet.

2.2. Model Architecture for Burnup

We adapt the DeepONet framework to our specific problem. We define our model's inputs and outputs as follows:

- Static Input ξ : A vector ξ in \mathbb{R}^s , where s is the total number of static input features.
- Dynamic Input u : The reactor power history $u(t)$ of time t is represented in the model as a discrete, variable-length time-series $\{x_i\}_{i=1}^{N_t}$. Here, N_t is the total number of time steps, and x_i in \mathbb{R}^d is the vector of d features at the i -th time step.
- Output y : The prediction target, which is a vector y in \mathbb{R}^m . Here, m is the total number of output values, corresponding to the m final nuclide concentrations of interest.

2.2.1. Branch Net: GRU for Time-Series

The core task of the Branch Net is to encode the variable-length power history $u(t)$. Simple RNNs suffer from vanishing/exploding gradients, making it difficult to capture long-term dependencies. LSTMs [10] and Gated Recurrent Units (GRUs) [11] solve this with gating mechanisms.

We choose a multi-layer GRU for its comparable performance to LSTM with greater computational efficiency. The GRU processes the entire sequence u and its final hidden state h is passed through a projection layer to produce the feature vector $b = N_{\text{branch}}(u; \theta_b) \in \mathbb{R}^p$.

2.2.2. Trunk Net: MLP for Static Features

The Trunk Net's role is to learn a basis for the output space based on the static inputs ξ . We use a standard Multi-Layer Perceptron (MLP). This network maps the static input vector ξ to the feature vector $t = N_{\text{trunk}}(\xi; \theta_t) \in \mathbb{R}^p$.

2.2.3. Feature Fusion and Output

Unlike the scalar outputs in the original DeepONet paper, which use a dot product (as shown in Figure 1), for our multi-output (vector) prediction task, we use the Hadamard product (element-wise multiplication \odot) to fuse the features, as it preserves more information than a simple dot product. This fused vector is then passed through a final affine layer to produce the m -dimensional output prediction:

$$\hat{y} = W (N_{\text{branch}}(u; \theta_b) \odot N_{\text{trunk}}(\xi; \theta_t)) + c \quad (2)$$

where the complete set of trainable parameters is $\theta = \{\theta_b, \theta_t, W, c\}$. θ_b and θ_t represent all weights and biases within the Branch and Trunk networks, respectively. W (dimensions $m \times p$) and c (dimensions $m \times 1$) are the weight matrix and bias vector of the final output layer.

2.3. Sim-to-Real Transfer Learning

Our training paradigm is crucial. The core challenge is the "Sim-to-Real gap" and the risk of "catastrophic forgetting" when fine-tuning on sparse data. Our two-stage approach mitigates this:

1. Pre-training: The model is trained on a large (thousands of samples) simulation dataset from NUIT. This teaches the model the general, complex, nonlinear physics of burnup, providing a robust "physics-informed" initialization.
2. Fine-tuning: The pre-trained model is then fine-tuned on the small (dozens of samples) experimental dataset. We use a lower learning rate (1×10^{-4} vs. 1×10^{-3} for pre-training) to gently adapt the pre-learned features to correct for real-world biases without overwriting the foundational physics knowledge.

3. DATASET CONSTRUCTION

3.1. Experimental Dataset (Target Domain)

The "gold standard" for calibration and validation is high-fidelity Radiochemical Assay (RCA) data from Post-Irradiation Examination (PIE) of actual SNF. We use internationally recognized benchmarks from the Obrigheim (KWO) and Trino Vercellese Pressurized Water Reactors (PWRs) [12]. This dataset includes 58 samples, covering a range of enrichments and burnup levels, and provides precise measurements for key isotopes. The experimental data are divided into training, validation, and test sets in a 6:2:2 ratio. Masking technology is applied to handle missing nuclides, and data cleaning is performed on the Am and Cm experimental results with excessive uncertainty using high-precision results from OpenMC.

3.2. Simulation Dataset (Source Domain)

Given the scarcity of experimental data, we generated a large-scale, parametric simulation dataset using the NUIT burnup code [13]. We systematically varied key initial parameters (e.g., ^{235}U enrichment from 2.5% to 4.6%, fuel density from 9.8 g/cm^3 to 10.5 g/cm^3) and used realistic power history templates based on the Obrigheim and Trino benchmarks. This process, using the ENDF/B-VIII.0 nuclear data library [4] and a fixed PWR single-group cross-section library, resulted in 5800 samples, which are divided into training, validation, and test sets in an 8:1:1 ratio. The resulting physically consistent

burnup cases serve as the foundation for pre-training the model.

3.3. Feature Engineering

Raw data is transformed into standardized tensors:

- Static Input (Trunk): A fixed-length vector of initial enrichment, heavy metal density, and U-235/U-238 mass fractions, scaled using Robust Scaling.
- Dynamic Input (Branch): A variable-length 5D time-series (time step, power, burnup step, cumulative time, cumulative burnup), also scaled using Robust Scaling.
- Output Target: A 10D vector of key nuclide concentrations (U, Pu isotopes, Am-241, Cm-242, Cs-137, Nd-148) in g/kgHM. Due to the vast (many orders of magnitude) difference in concentrations, we apply Min-Max Scaling to the target vector, scaling all values to $[0, 1]$.

4. EXPERIMENTS AND RESULTS

4.1. Experimental Setup

- Metrics: R^2 Score, and distributions of relative error (MAPE, Median, 95th Percentile).
- Baselines:
 1. NUIT Direct Simulation: The original physics simulation results.
 2. Train from Scratch: The DeepONet model trained only on the small experimental dataset.
 3. Fine-tuned Model: Our proposed model (Pre-trained + Fine-tuned).

4.2. Loss Function: MAE vs. MSE

We chose MAE over MSE as the loss function. As shown in Figure 2, training with MSE (Section 4.2) results in a highly volatile validation loss, with sharp spikes caused by outliers. The resulting "best" model is often just a product of a "lucky" validation batch. In contrast, MAE (Section 4.2) provides a much more stable training dynamic, as its linear penalty is robust to outliers. This leads to a more reliable and generalizable model.

(a) MAE Loss (Stable Validation)

(b) MSE Loss (Volatile Validation)

Figure 2. Comparison of MAE and MSE loss functions during pre-training.

4.3. Pre-training Results

After pre-training on simulation data, the model demonstrates a strong grasp of the underlying physics (Figure 3). For U-235 and U-238, the error distributions are narrow, zero-centered Gaussians. For higher-order actinides (Pu-241, Am-241, Cm-242), the distributions are wider and slightly skewed, correctly reflecting the physical reality that errors accumulate and amplify along the transmutation chain. This confirms the model is a “physics-knowledgeable” base.

Figure 3. Relative error distribution of the pre-trained model on the simulation test set.

4.4. Fine-tuning Results: Bridging the Sim-to-Real Gap

The fine-tuned model’s predictions on the experimental dataset are outstanding. Figure 4 shows the parity plots, where data points for nearly all nuclides align tightly along the $y = x$ “perfect prediction” line. R^2 scores exceed 0.99 for most nuclides, demonstrating a near-perfect fit to reality. The remaining nuclides also have R^2 scores above 0.90, indicating strong accuracy across all tested isotopes.

Figure 4. Parity plots (Predicted vs. True) for the fine-tuned model on the experimental dataset.

4.5. Quantitative Comparison

The comparison in Figure 5 and Table I provides the definitive proof of our method’s value.

- NUIT Direct Simulation (Green Bar): This baseline quantifies the Sim-to-Real gap. While accurate for some fission products (Cs-137, Nd-148), it fails catastrophically for higher actinides, with errors

Figure 5. Performance comparison of the three models on the experimental dataset.

Table I. Comparison of Maximum Relative Error (%) on the experimental dataset.

Nuclide	Maximum Relative Error (%)		
	Fine-tuned Model	Train from Scratch	NUIT Direct Simulation
U235	6.07	31.60	34.50
U238	0.61	0.60	0.51
Pu239	6.98	7.49	20.25
Pu240	9.85	5.08	48.42
Pu241	14.71	9.52	75.46
Pu242	17.05	65.64	65.18
Am241	7.77	15.88	75.30
Cm242	15.81	22.61	88.88
Cs137	4.29	6.70	3.25
Nd148	5.48	7.57	3.02

reaching 70-90% (e.g., Cm-242, Am-241). This is the problem we aimed to solve.

- Train from Scratch (Orange Bar): This model's performance is erratic. It fails completely on some nuclides (e.g., U-235, Pu-242) and shows high variance. Lacking a physics prior, it cannot generalize from the sparse data and overfits, making it unreliable.
- Fine-tuned Model (Blue Bar): Our model is the clear winner. It dramatically corrects the large errors from the NUIT simulation, reducing the max error for U-235 from 34.50% to 6.07%, for Pu-239 from 20.25% to 6.98%, for Pu-242 from 65.18% to 17.05%, for Cm-242 from 88.9% to 15.8%, and for Am-241 from 75.3% to 7.8%. It learns to correct the simulation's bias. Furthermore, it avoids the catastrophic failures of the "from-scratch" model, demonstrating the robust, regularizing effect of physics-based pre-training. Meanwhile, for Cs137 and Nd148, the model maintains high accuracy, performing between the "Train from Scratch" and "NUIT Direct Simulation" approaches.. It is the most accurate and reliable model across the board.

5. CONCLUSIONS

We developed a DeepONet-based surrogate model using a Sim-to-Real transfer learning paradigm to predict nuclide concentrations in spent fuel. This approach is not just a fast approximation but a "data-physics-fused enhancement" demonstrably more accurate than the original physics simulation.

Our key findings show that pre-training on a large simulation dataset is essential for building a robust, physics-based knowledge base and preventing overfitting. Subsequent fine-tuning on small experimental datasets effectively corrects the simulation's inherent systemic biases.

The resulting model bridges the "Sim-to-Real gap," achieving exceptional accuracy and significantly reducing prediction errors for challenging higher-order actinides. This robust framework is also extensible to other reactor types and key physics predictions, such as decay heat.

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